

Human DRI session 1: Strengthening the case for investing in dRTP career pathways

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As digital technologies become more pervasive, powerful, complex, and costly, the need for a resilient and effective Digital Research Infrastructure (DRI) profession becomes increasingly urgent. Digital Research Technical Professionals (dRTPs) are essential for the efficient development and delivery of high-quality Research and Innovation (R&I), and for increasing the visibility and recognition of the profession. However, career progression and the sustainability of our “human DRI” have not kept pace.

In this session, we discussed current and future strategies to incentivise the development of sustainable, resilient, and effective digital functions with the commensurate critical mass of people and resource to enable the development of career pathways and progression frameworks within Research Organisations (ROs).

UKRI Strategy

Through the [people and teams plan](#), UKRI has committed to using the range of levers at its disposal, primarily its role as an investor in R&I and as a policy organisation, to incentivise the development of cross cutting digital infrastructure capability (human DRI). This includes the recently launched [People and teams assessment pilot](#) to embed assessment criteria into UKRI’s investment decisions, supporting ROs applying for UKRI funding to develop their technical and specialist functions. This aim is to ensure UKRI investments strengthen these critical capabilities enabling the delivery of innovative ideas and high-quality outputs while maximising value for money and the resilience of the R&I system.

People and teams aligns to a range of programmes across UKRI to support the DRI profession, which includes, for example, UKRI’s recently published [draft research data policy](#) and investments from across the research councils.

Key themes, Recommendations, and Next Steps

Team research¹ should be more than the team of investigators and project leads. It requires recognising the wide range of R&I professions that improve the impact, quality, and reliability of research outputs and outcomes. Team research is most effective when it starts early, at the formulation of funding applications. This approach ensures the right technical and specialist expertise is available to strengthen the quality of the hypothesis, and its testing, but also to build the capability needed to deliver the proposed work effectively.

In assessing applications for funding, academic peer reviewers, especially those outside of specialist disciplines (e.g., computer science), are not always well equipped to assess certain aspects of the grant, such as staff development, data management, resourcing and staffing for the wide range of roles needed for increasingly complex and interdisciplinary research. Conversely dRTP professionals,

¹ Often referred to as “Team Science” in STEM disciplines

along with other R&I contributors, are experts in these areas and may help reduce the review burden on academics by allowing them to focus on the disciplinary aspects of the proposal.

The dRTP community, along with other technical and specialist roles in R&I were bought in and aware of the need for change. Senior leadership in ROs was similarly engaged. However, a key outstanding constituency were the academic and departmental leadership community in ROs, audiences that the dRTP community, and policy organisations like UKRI often found challenging to reach. A set of clear, concise, and compelling messages as well as a credible plan for engaging these groups were strongly recommended.

These insights, and recommendations provided the attendees from the dRTP community, will be used to support the development of UKRI policy and strategy. For example, working on increasing RTP and technical expertise on funding decision panels across UKRI councils.

Attendee Insights

Participants provided their perspectives during round-table discussions, with contributions recorded via the Mentimeter platform. A summary of the discussion topics is presented below:

Prompt: What else could, or should, be done?

Cultural change and enhanced structural support were expected to enable greater recognition of diverse roles and professions in R&I. A shift in attitudes across universities and funding bodies was regarded as necessary to ensure contributions beyond traditional academic outputs are valued.

Integration of dRTPs into peer review processes was recommended to help strengthen the assessment of capability to deliver appropriately within research proposals, as academic peer reviewers were not always felt to be the best equipped to evaluate these aspects. Academic applicants may lack expertise in areas such as costings and data management plans which result in these elements not always being accurately represented or assessed in applications. The inclusion of dRTPs with relevant expertise was considered a way to mitigate this risk. Additional involving dRTPs early in the grant writing process was viewed as a way to improve consistency within technical areas, such as data management plans, and enhance proposal development. Thus, increasing the accuracy and quality of funding applications.

Future funding mechanisms were encouraged to provide adequate support for the dRTP community to address existing risks. Strengthening support for dRTPs teams was viewed as critical to ensure long-term sustainability and enhance innovation beyond the lifetime of individual projects.

Promoting ground up approaches to change, such as broadening entry routes into the profession through internships and apprenticeships, was identified as a way to facilitate greater diversity in R&I. Expanding career development opportunities, including case studies to showcase successful role models and creating networking platforms, was highlighted as important for fostering creativity and knowledge exchange in R&I.

Prompt: Who are the key stakeholder and what messages will reach them?

Responses identified a wide range of stakeholders across institutional, governmental, and professional services. While senior leadership was generally perceived to be receptive, departmental and unit leadership often constituted a point where messages did not reach, making this group a key constituency for further engagement.

Sharing a strong vision for the importance of dRTPs was emphasised. Without the skills of dRTPs on relevant research projects, the capability to deliver robust, high quality, and high impact research effectively, would be constrained. Additionally, this approach would improve value for money by ensuring costs were accurately represented in research applications to funders, thereby supporting the long-term financial sustainability of research; and by increasing the robustness and useability of research outcomes.

A collaborative approach, involving engagement with other networks and closer alignment with initiatives such as the Technician Commitment, was considered essential to enhance the opportunity for curiosity driven research, facilitate knowledge exchange, and reduce barriers between roles.

Prompt: Are there other ways to make this case? What evidence can we marshal?

Evidence based advocacy supported by relatable narratives was considered essential to strengthen the case for dRTPs. Quantifying impact and inefficiencies in current ways of working was viewed as critical to ensure there is clear evidence to stakeholders, demonstrating the financial implications and underscoring the value of these roles in academic research. This evidence would assist in mitigating institutional risks. Evidence was suggested to include estimates of the costs of not having dRTPs on relevant research projects and modelling the opportunity costs of inefficient digital research infrastructure.

Another key recommendation was to illustrate the tangible benefits of dRTPs through case studies, such as examples of time saved by Research Software Engineers, successful projects delivered by dRTPs, and the benefits of dRTPs to research impact. This evidence was expected to help universities to take on perceived 'risks' before returns of the inclusion of dRTPs became evident.

The need to raise the profile of non-traditional research outputs was repeatedly emphasised, reinforcing the community's role in enhancing the quality and impact of research through diverse contributions while also increasing research visibility and transparency across R&I.

Prompt: What do you need from UKRI, to help the argument for change within your own organisation?

The need for policy interventions, funding mechanisms, and guidance from funding bodies was emphasised to strengthen the case for cultural and structural change. Representation of dRTPs on funding recommendation panels was regarded as a means of recognising the value of the wide range of R&I professions that improve research quality while reducing the burden of peer review on our academic community.

Gathering evidence of the benefits of including RTPs in diverse research teams was considered essential for supporting advocacy efforts within ROs. Suggested data included time, efficiency, and research quality gains from dRTP involvement in research projects. Data collection ideas proposed were focus groups and case studies to provide real world examples of the benefits dRTPs contributed to R&I, thereby strengthening the case for change.